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CALL FOR PAPERS

1. The Editorial Board of the Benue State University Journal of Education (BSUJE), an annual publication of the faculty of Education of the University, will consider for publication in the subsequent issues of the journal in June and September yearly, a variety of high quality manuscripts on issues relating to any field of education. Although theoretical and philosophical papers are welcome, more emphasis will be placed on empirical research work.
2. Three copies of each article intended for publication, accompanied by a processing fee of N500 in cash or bank draft payable at Makurdi should be submitted not later than 30th December every year.

All correspondence should be addressed to:

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3 Articles submitted to the Journal should be scholarly and original contributions of authors and should not be under consideration for any other publication at the same time. Articles should not be more than twelve pages on A4, doubled spaced typing on one side of the page only, (including abstract and references), tables and figures should be kept to the barest minimum and should be included in the text. All tables and figures should be properly captioned and numbered serially throughout the text

4 Each article should be arranged as follows:

1. Title of the article, name of the author(s) and affiliation(s) all on the same page.

ii. Title of the article, and abstract of not more than 120 words followed by the main body of the article

5 Quotations of more than fifty words should be indented three spaces typed double spaced. All shorter quotations should be enclosed in quotation marks.

6 References should follow the latest APA style. endnotes and footnoting are not allowed.

7 Ideas expressed in the articles are personal to the contributors as such, the authors are responsible for the views they express. Contributors should obtain written permission to use materials for which they do not have copyright.

8 Articles sent for publication will be subjected to expert review and only those found publishable by assessors will be published in the Journal.

9 The Editorial Board will not enter into correspondence with authors whose articles are not found publishable.

10 Contributors should enclose two self-addressed stamped envelopes.

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DEAN'S COMMENTS

The world today has become a global village and information Technology is vital to the education Industry as it is to all other sectors.

This volume on Information Technology and National Development comes handy. The papers presented would add to the rich knowledge bank available to staff and students and to the benefit of the Nation. It is hoped that you will find this volume an indispensable material for the development of IT.

Prof. (Mrs) B.O Ker

Dean, Faculty of Education

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Open and distant learning Education through Television broadcasting, Implication for counselling

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Abstract

Education is offered through television broadcasting in several parts of the world today. Major reasons for such an approach are to increase accessibility to knowledge and improve more on information technology for larger and increasing numbers of people who are ready to learn in the society. The world has become a global village that it is a useful instructional strategy for reaching people. More so, that several other workers who cannot afford to leave their jobs for full-time studies are benefited. In essence, educational television is something every open and distant educator should incorporate in his or her studies because various institutions are increasingly less able to cope with costs of offering education to the needy

Introduction:

Television broadcasting is an instructional device; as One of the means of communication broad ideas of government countries, institutions and organizations. it is increasing in popularity with the arrival of the video recording cassettes; commercial television stations have slots devoted to learning in open and distant system of Education. In many parts of the world, television broadcasting is used to enhance education of people whose residences are far or near, people who may have difficulties with the traditional mode of study. Daughtrey (1974) in Nwozor j.C. (2001) state that television teaching is popularized by the way modern youths spend their time. She reports of a research, which shows that: “An

American School Child spends more time watching television than he would spend in the college classroom during four years.”

This shows from the above statement that television is replacing both parent and teacher as the primary educator of American Children. j Ogunmilade (1984) in Nwozor J. C. (2001) states in his book titled ‘Media in

Education’ that educational television takes place in most of the world. Countries that have practiced it for long include USA, Europe, Canada, Australia, Japan, Italy, Russia, Samoa, Nigeria, South Africa, Ghana, Colombia, India, Zambia, South Vietnam, United Arab Republic, Niger, Ivory Coast and Cuba. Furthermore, he show that developing countries adopted education television (ETV) before the

Sixties, while developing countries are only recently becoming aware of its impact. For example, the popular ‘Sesame Street’ programme provides a world of learning experience for the young in both the developed and developing countries. A Year Book by the Common-wealth University, published in 1994, showed that Educational Television is utilized by four Universities in Nigeria namely: Abia State University, Utuluru; University of Abuja; Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, and University of Lagos. There are other educational television outfits in College of Technology, Enugu, Federal Polytechnic, Oko, Anambra State and the recent National Open University studies centers. In some of these institutions, the name for ETV is “university of the Air” In addition, since the implementation of Open and Distant Learning (ODL) in most countries, the television broadcasting plays prominent roles wherever there is electricity.

For Open University programmes in Nigeria, the Education Television at Tejuoso had been commissioned to air all necessary broadcasts. A unit within the National Open University, for example, works in conjunction with the Television Station to prepare, produce and air the various programmes to students. Other learning institutes or centers may soon be linked with the Television broadcast nationally.

Definition of terms used:

ETV Educational television is a response to knowledge explosion. It is a means by which course credit is granted during academic study via television, radio, newspaper, the mail and telephone. It also includes human mentors, tutorials,

teachers, and facilitators, Mechanically controlled devices, humans. Computer networks and textbooks are used to help teach the learners.

- ITV:- Instructional Television is an effective distance education delivery system just as ETV.

- ODL:- Open and Distant learning

Characteristics of the Open Distant Learner.

“Education is a companion which no misfortune can depress, no crime can destroy, no enemy can alienate, no despotism can enslave” (Joseph Addison, 1672-1719). In the Open Distant Learning system, students are adults, most of who are well over the age of 20. On the average, they are older than students in the conventional university. Most of them have jobs and families, and now add another dimension to their life by going into part time studies, within, hopefully, a virtual environment. A number of open and distant learners had broken contact with formal school situations for long time and now have to return to education after a gap of so many years,. re-entering. studying and learning situation may become rather hard to handle. They, are from. different professions ranging from Church \workers or Muslim Clerics, businessmen/women, farmers, artisans, petty traders; others could be politicians etc. All these are faced with long and tedious work to do and journey to cover.

The characteristics of the open and distant learner are as varied as the number of students are different from the other, yet all of them are’ distant learning students whose main role and interest is to learn. This is a very challenging task. Yet under the best of circumstances, this challenging task requires motivation, dedication, planning, strategizing and the ability to analyze and apply the information being taught Schuerner (1993) in Ipaye B. (2004) say that in a distant education setting, the process of student learning is more complex for several reasons.

He argues that Distant Students have a variety of reasons for taking courses. Some students are interested in obtaining a degree to qualify for a better job. This is very much true of Nigeria.

One important factor in open distant. learning (ODL) is that of isolation of the student. The learner usually feels isolated. He or she misses the motivational and

emotional factors arising from the contact or competition with other students. It takes longer for student-lecturer rapport to develop.

The argument is that without face-to-face contact, distant students may not be at ease with their lecturers as an “Individual” and may be uncomfortable with the learning situation. The open distant learner relies heavily on technology, which, typically serves as the conduit.. through. which information and communication flow well.

The Need for Open and Distant Education In Nigeria

The following are some reasons, which have been advanced in favour of open and distant education system in Nigeria.

According to Thomas D. (1995), these are: Increase in Accessibility of Education to Worker:

ii. The open and distant learning have allowed a large number of workers increased access to education, Lack of job security if moved into full time studies has made workers to join open and distant education to acquire more knowledge and skills.

ii. Providing Education for Social Equity:

The under-pining philosophy of open and distance education is that of Social censuring, and economic mobility to deprive members.

These objectives are being achieved because people who cannot obtain qualitative education by conventional system are afforded through open and distant education system.

iii. Meeting the academic needs of people due to admission problems:

The open and distant education system helps to meet their academic needs of people due to admission problems. Annually, to Nwana (1991) about two hundred and fifty thousand applicants vie for only fifty thousand vacancies in our universities. If university education can only be acquired through only full—time process, the many qualified candidates would undoubtedly be denied university education and this would result to shortage of manpower, thereby resulting to retrogression of the Society.

iv. Enhancing a long Education:

Finally, the era of technology has changed work environment so much that workers are afraid of obsolescence in their skills. This situation calls for continuous education of workers, periodic refresher courses, etc. Hence, the only hope towards achieving these, i.e. in open and distant education system, is which the opportunity for learning while working.

Reasons for Education Television (ETV) in Open and Distance Learning.

Education Television (ETV) is an effective distant education delivery system and is used in the following ways, for the open distant learner: -

i. Delivery of a single lesson:

Programmes address one Specific Topic Theme or concept. The lesson is fully taught, covering the introduction, the body of the lesson, an over view, or summary and then evaluation questions.

i. Delivery of a selected unit:

This consists of a series of lectures designed to cover a unit of work as described in the course curriculum.

iii. Full Course:

Programs from one or more ETV series may be integrated into a full semester typically in conjunction with instructional print materials.

The Education or Instructional Television (ITV) or (ETV) may either be passive or interactive.

Passive: (ETV) or (ITV) typically involves pre-producing programs, which are distributed by video based on technologies such as broadcast, cable or satellite. In contrast,-

Interactive: (ETV) or (ITV) Provides opportunities for viewer interaction, either with a live instructor or a participating student site. For example, two-way television with two-way audio allows all students to view and interact with the lecturer Lochte (1993). At the same time, camera at remote sites allow the lecturer

to view all participating students. It is also possible to configure the system so that all student sites may view one another.

Benefits of Educational Television (Instructional) are:

i) To most distant learners, television is quite familiar though many might not have used the television for any other purposes than as an entertainment box, an information provider, and a viewing screen. This means that to most distant learners, the television is mainly for listening to newscast. It is assumed however that it will be a familiar educational medium for them as well.

ii) For educational purposes, motion and visuals can be combined in a single format so that complex or abstract concepts can be illustrated through visual simulation. It is well known that a picture tells the story effectively than a thousand words.

A picture combined with motions and words surely will have more effect than just the word alone or the pictures alone.

iii) Educational (Instructional)

Television is an effective way to take students to new environments (New sites, a foreign country, or factory at work, though the microscopic time and space can be collapsed so that events can be captured and relayed as they happen. More than any other medium, the television reduces to the barest minimum, the distance in education.

iv) More females, saddled with domestic chores, ('parenting or child bearing and agricultural), can enroll in university level education.

This is because they could study at their homes or at their convenient hour without spending as much money as in the traditional universities.

v) The community values education the more, welcomes it and more people become Learners. ETV helps to eradicate literacy faster.

vi) More students who enroll stay on till they finish, there by maximizing the utility of human resources in the institutions.

vii) Access to education is more open through ETV (ITV) than any other medium because admission to study and earn grades is freer.

Opportunities and accessibility are modified by reducing those features that prevent schools. The learner's motivations, anxieties, conveniences.

preferences and language capacity are provided for.

There is flexibility in time scheduling. The organization, workload, pace and time for each major component is adjustable. Unhelpful preconditions for admission such as whether buildings are available, whether programmes fit into present structures, whether procedures to adopt agree with established ones and other assumptions usually preventing people's access to education are accommodated. It is very effective for introducing, summarizing, and reviewing concepts. It can be used effectively as a motivational tool.

Limitation! Cost Effectiveness of ETV (ITV)

Broadcast quality ETV (ITV) is expensive to create.

ii) Video production is time consuming and can be technically demanding, often requiring relatively sophisticated production facilities and equipment.

iii) Most precourses use a mass media approach to instruction aimed at the average student. As a result, they can be ineffective in serving students with special needs.

iv) Television broadcasts lack individuals touch;

v) Sites choosing to interactively participate in an ETV (TTV) Program may require specialized equipment. facilities and staffing.

vi) When used passively without interaction, instructional effectiveness can be limited. Unless Professionally produced. completed ETV (ITV) Programmes often look amateurish - voice completed, ETV (ITV) Programmes can be difficult to revise and update. Many students still view their television education programmes as if they were viewing or listening to news broadcast, Ipaye B. (2004, pg. 96). - Strategies !Techniques needed in using ETV (ITV). use ETV (ITV) effectively for your education you have to be visually oriented. You also have to learn to think in visual terms. You have dual advantage of hearing and seeing. According Ipaye B.

(2004) “it will greatly enhance your understanding you see the following visually presented and then verbally explained”.

Outlines or lists Key Points; complex material in a step-by-step fashion; Relationships; Information that needs to be summarized for retention and Recall. You should pay detailed attention to the following that are used during the broadcast or presentation; Pictures:- to show what things look like;

Diagrams:- To illustrate conceptual relationships, organizations, and structure of content material.

Maps:- To show spatial relationships.

Graphs:- Tables and Charts to summarize information. Take advantage of the following techniques in television's ability to show movement as:—

Demonstrate the operation of tools and equipment:

Demonstrate skills that you are expected to emulate: Try to follow administrations as presenter uses animation, slow motion or time lapse photography;

Learn all you can possibly do in 'ery short time from the new places or situations shown which were not otherwise in your experience;

Follow each step for experiments being conducted and observe the process.

Grasp as quickly as possible, the spatial, three — dimensional qualities of an objective or structure as shown on the screen;

As Primary Source Material presentation, try to do your analysis or follow carefully and attentively the analysis done by the presenter.

Conditions that Assure success for Education (Instructional) Television. Daughterty (1974) in Nwazor J.C (2001) states three sets of instructions that assure success in the use of educational television in Norfolk (Virginia, USA).

The conditions are grouped into three namely: -

What to do before the telecast, during the telecast and after the telecast.

The Instructions are adapted to show that before the telecast, teachers should: -

Know exactly what is to be presented

ii) Prepare students for the content to be viewed through preliminary teaching as well as get them ready for a follow-up of their class;

iii) Turn on the television set at stated broadcast time and adjust appropriately;

iv) Teachers should be able to watch telecast and student's reaction. During the telecast, teachers should:

i) Watch the telecast with the students

ii) Show enthusiasm and respond as required by the presenter;

iii) Listen 'effectively (intelligently not noisily or indifferently) and watch by taking useful notes of points made.

iv) Select Clues in the telecast that will be useful to the class later

v) Observe students reactions during the telecast so as to utilize them in follow-up teaching. After the telecast, teachers should do the following things: -

i) Turn off the television set immediately

ii) Start a follow-up on the telecast if time permits, it is advisable to adopt a period that allows this step.

iii) Re-emphasize important points or clarify and explain them more lucidly;

iv) Initiate discussion of concepts or ideas as students demand.

v) Allow Interaction between teacher and students and among students on topics or issues.

vi) Design assignments or activities that will help meet students' needs and abilities.

vii) Re-teach issues not exhausted in the telecast by using adequate strategies within the school such as overhead Projectors, videotape records of that telecast. and field trips, among others.

mplications for counseling:

The main goal of guidance, whether educational or vocational, is to effect a permanent change in human behaviours after the presentation of Educational Television Technology. The counsellors, complete acceptance of the students as worthy students, his or her relaxed approach to encourage Educational Television would enable them win their trust. Trust — building is an important step the process of the Counsellor's rebuilding of the distant open learner's self-esteem and confidence that they can make it in life. By the use of ETV (ITV)

Counsellor can first diffuse the fear of failure in the adult learner, inspire him/her, especially the elderly ones to work hard to achieve, self-sufficiency and independence.

The counsellors in the distant open learning should keep his students adequately informed about new discoveries in Television that relate to the improvement of their students and also teach them on time management.

Students should check the subject or broadcast beforehand and try to do some preliminary reading and thinking (take special note f all reference immaterial to it that appear in your study materials, you may benefit from it,).

Conclusion/Suggestion:

This paper has focused on educational (instructional) television as one of the modern technologies used in open Distani

Learner Educational System in Nigeria now. The definition of. Educational (instructional) television and where it is adopted in Nigeria and abroad is highlighted. Characteristics of the students involved in open and Distant System were discussed; the need for their studies in Nigeria, reasons for the users of education television; benefits of them, cost limitations effectiveness were discussed too. Also many strategies /techniques needed in using them were stated and conditions needed for their success were reviewed too.

The foregoing discussion posses a challenge for many Counselors and other educators who probably were not taught how to use telecasts in Counselling and teaching. It is important that such Counsellors should go in for in-service training.

It is suggested that syllabuses for teachers' development should include flexible-learning procedures such as how to utilize the television, video recorder, radio and film strips.

The students should be properly guided in educational broadcast production, including all the sub-components that make-up a final broadcast. It is also generally suggested that educational television be emphasized strongly to help bridge the gap between the literate and non-literate members of the Nigerian society as a whole.

However, the primary aim of this ETV is that students, should be well-equipped for this task and the Federal Government, State and Local Levels should be ready to give them full support financially for the programme to succeed.

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